

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: MABJAIA****FIRST NAME: AUGUSTO****PROGRAM CODE: DEPI****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 1%

The author used the following software: MSWord 2016 on Windows 8

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Academic Essay (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 7-14)
2. Punctuation Marks and their Usage (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 7-14)
3. American VS British English (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 7-14)
4. Plagiarism (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 7-14)
5. Chicago Style Guide and Usage (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 7-14)

SCHOLARLY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

Taking the decision to study Philosophy Doctor (Ph.D.) in Epidemiology and Biostatistics constituted a major challenge for me because of my English language limitations and the non-presential system used at this international university.

When I started navigating the Learning Management System (LMS) and reading the ACA-401D course pack, period one, it introduced me to the world that I can call the process of academic essay writing. From this initial journey, I could be familiar with the teaching methodology and technology used in EUCLID, and I started to feel more comfortable because I noticed that there are available tools to help me overcome the initial barriers. I can see the route ahead and the effort required for a successful journey in this Program.

For the ACA-401D course, I found the provided materials (ACA-401D course pack and video) with well-detailed explanations with elucidative and practical examples. The course is already consolidating my knowledge in a matter of scholarly writing based on some established academic rules and styles.

Thus, in this response paper, I will be discussing five key concepts of the provided materials: academic essays, punctuation marks and their usage, Americans Vs British English, plagiarism, and Chicago Style. While discussing the concepts, I had the opportunity to clarify my initial understanding (sometimes was wrong), as I found it necessary to go back and re-read or watch the provided materials.

2) ACADEMIC ESSAY

The writing process of every prose varies largely according to the author's objectives as some proeses intend to describe personal feelings, experiences, thoughts, past events, and so forth. At the same time, others are problem-solving-oriented through producing scientifically sound information, which is an addition to the academic community and/or can also be used in the process of decision-making.

For my doctoral program, the latter, academic essay, is the main focus of the program as it "... seeks to provide answers to hypotheses, aiming to communicate ideas based on evidence" (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 7). To facilitate the process of generating solutions for a problem or creating new ideas from the academic essay, the author proposes some helpful rules that guide this process, from the definition of the research problem to the essay handing in. The researcher's willingness to engage in this adventure plays a key role in the way to overcome typical challenges of this exercise; as Cleenewerck and Gulma advise, "one of the initial things required for writing is to have enough time to read, research the topic, think, and write. It is never advisable to procrastinate" (7). On the other hand, the organization of the academic essay should be simple and divided into three main parts: introduction, body, and conclusion (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 10).

The introduction section brings general information about the topic being discussed in a "funneled" way. For example: how the problem is global, in the continent, country, province/region, and or in the study place (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 10). The body is described as where researchers answer the question using obtained data and the literature review, while the conclusion brings the most important findings of the research (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 10).

While writing an academic essay, it is important to avoid situations of plagiarism as this carries academic penalties that can go up to failing a course (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 14). The authors present situations of how to avoid plagiarism and describe it as robbing ideas from previously published sources; this includes, but is not limited to, inappropriate citation and quotation, using synonyms or original idea's words, and lack of referencing of the original source (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 14).

3) PUNCTUATION MARKS AND THEIR USAGE

The art of writing needs to be ruled out to express the real thoughts of the author and to invite the readers to engage in the understanding of the exposed content. Thus, punctuation marks play an essential role in organizing, separating, and clarifying ideas.

The ACA-401D provides a comprehensive approach to how and when to use punctuation marks (with practical examples), although Cleenewerck and Gulma advise the rational use of them as a general rule (16). It means that abusive use of punctuation marks can confuse the readers resulting in misinterpretation of the content.

I understood that some punctuation marks can vary according to the English version: USA or UK. For example, in quotation marks, using American English, periods are used outside the quotation, while in the UK version, periods are put inside (Cleenewerck n.d.).

4) AMERICAN VS BRITISH ENGLISH

Similar but different, the main differences between the two versions of English are related to spelling, pronunciation, and meaning. These differences were unclear to me since I am from a non-English-speaking country (Mozambique). While Portuguese is the country's official language, English is learned in secondary schools, and Standard British English is the official version in the country.

American English has been gaining space (over British English) worldwide due to the country's influence sphere in international affairs (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 25). This is the main reason I chose to use American English in my papers to facilitate my academic journey since I believe I will be in contact with many materials published in American English Version. While choosing American English was easy for me, I am aware that the British version will somehow attempt me during my writing. Cleenewerck shows that *Microsoft Office Word* provides some useful tools in function: *Review – Language – Set Proofing Language – US English* that can help detect spelling errors (Cleenewerck n.d.).

The American and British English dispute is familiar, but in a different situation: Portuguese against Brazilian. Both are considered Portuguese languages, and the official one in former Portuguese colonies is the version from Portugal. Still, the version of Brazil is common in academic papers due to its high level of publishing papers. Several times, I had to do an extra exercise of re-writing Brazilian Portuguese in the accepted Portuguese version in my country (That was before learning the use of square brackets and *sic* expression).

5) PLAGIARISM

An anti-ethic practice consists of using or presenting - as yours - words, ideas, statistics, and other relevant information with lack or without recognizing the original author or source through due citation and referencing (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 34).

After reading ACA-401D course pack, I learned that students and researchers can plagiarize even if unaware of such practices. While aware plagiarism would consist in purposively omitting information about the original author, the unaware one would come in two different ways: on the one hand as a lack of knowledge of citation, quotation, and referencing, and on the other hand due to the unclear delimitation of what can be considered as a piece of common knowledge, and therefore no need to cite.

Regardless of the situation, Cleenewerck and Gulma advertises that plagiarism is unacceptable and wrong (2021, 34). The authors present situations that can help researchers to avoid it and enhance the difference between making in-text citations for short quotes and paraphrases and the use of footnotes (a detailed reference description of the original source) (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 34-38).

6) CHICAGO STYLE GUIDE AND USAGE

There are rules that writers need to follow to write academic essays, and the Chicago Manual of Style provides useful tools to make the writing process simple, mainly for American English users. While there are several styles that can be used according to the region or field of study, EUCLID recommends the use of the Turabian style which “has been revised to conform with the Chicago Style” (EUCLID, n.d.).

Style Guide is a standard operational procedure that intends to conduct writers of research papers in order to produce well-structured, coherent, and appropriate page formatting and grammar jobs (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 44-57; Cleenewerck, n.d.). A technological resource such as *Zotero* has proven to be useful for me as, before, I used the manual system for referencing or citation. The free online version of *Grammarly* is also helping me - as a non-native English speaker - with spell and syntax checking as well as plagiarism detection.

The ACA-401D course pack explains and exemplifies how and when to use abbreviations, capitalization, quotations, italics, compound words, numbers, tables, footnotes, endnotes, bibliographies, and page formats. For page formatting, Cleenewerck shows that the formatting can also be performed in *Microsoft Office Word* using the *Home tab*. Different automated format functions are presented in this program for headings and subheadings, quotations, references, and many others (Cleenewerck, n.d.).

7) CONCLUSION

Researchers write academic essays to produce a scientifically sound solution for a certain problem. Divided into three main parts - introduction, body, and conclusion – the project comprehends crucial phases from problem definition to essay handing in.

The task of writing publishable research papers is guided by rules and styles that vary according to institutions, and for EUCLID, the recommended one is Turabian for in-text referencing. The tools such as Zotero and Grammarly, and Microsoft Office Word make the writing process easier and more efficient throughout the production of academic work.

Before the writing process, it is important to make an informed choice of which between American and British English language will be used. While the two versions have more in common, some differences do exist, and they are related to spelling, pronunciation, and meaning. Differences are also noticeable in the style guide, which can vary according to the institution's preference.

While writing an academic essay, it is important to avoid plagiarism as it is considered academically unethical and punishable. But can be avoided through appropriate citation and referencing of the original source.

REFERENCES

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